

Tetrakispyridine-2-carboxylatoniobium(IV) and Trispyridine-2-carboxylatoxononiobium(V)

A. V. SAHA and SUBHA SEN.

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science,
Calcutta-700 009Manuscript received 14 December 1982, revised 29
July 1983, accepted 21 July 1984

NO niobium complex containing pyridine-2-carboxylate anion as the ligand is reported in the literature. This communication describes the preparation and properties of tetrakispyridine-2-carboxylatoniobium(IV) as a monomeric violet-red complex and its colourless oxidation product, trispyridine-2-carboxylatoxononiobium(V). The niobium(IV) complex is interesting¹ because of its unquenched magnetic moment corresponding to d^1 configuration free from Nb-Nb interaction.

Experimental

Reagents, apparatus and analysis: Potassium disulphatoniobate(III) was prepared by the reported method² using niobium(V) oxide (Fluka, 99.8%). All other reagents were of appropriate purity. Nitrogen gas was purified by washing with acidified Cr^{II} solution. IR spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR 20 in KBr pellets, the electronic spectra on a Hilger UVISPEK and the conductance values were measured by a Philips' RCL bridge. Molecular weight determination was carried out in camphor by Rast's method. Magnetic susceptibility was measured with a Gouy balance. Niobium was determined as Nb_2O_5 by ignition and C, H and N analysed by micro combustion.

Tetrakispyridine-2-carboxylatoniobium(IV), $Nb(C_6H_4NO_2)_4$: 200 mg of freshly prepared potassium disulphatoniobate(III) tetrahydrate was freed from sulphuric acid by washing with ethanol. The solid was allowed to react with 400 mg of pyridine-2-carboxylic acid hydrochloride in 5 ml water. The deep red solution was immediately extracted with 125 ml chloroform in portions and the extract was evaporated in a rotary vacuum evaporator. The experiment upto this stage was carried out in nitrogen atmosphere. The dry material is sufficiently stable to permit further experiments in presence of air. The product obtained was extracted with 100 ml dry benzene to remove any oxidised $NbO(C_6H_4NO_2)_3$. The benzene solution was then evaporated to afford violet-red needles and dried. The powdered solid was heated to 150° in a stream of dry oxygen-free nitrogen when free ligand present as impurity sublimed off to yield the purified product (250 mg) (Found: C, 49.5; H, 2.28; N, 9.7; Nb, 16.6%. $Nb(C_6H_4NO_2)_4$: Calcd. C, 49.8; H, 2.75; N, 9.6; Nb, 16.0%).

Trispyridine-2-carboxylatoxononiobium(V), $NbO(C_6H_4NO_2)_3$: 100 mg of tetrakispyridine-2-carboxylatoniobium(IV) in 10 ml of chloroform was oxidised by passing moist chlorine gas until decolo-

urisation of the solution was complete. The precipitated pyridine-2-carboxylic acid hydrochloride was removed and the solution evaporated. The dry mass was washed with benzene to yield the product (75 mg) (Found: N, 9.0; Nb, 19.6%. $NbO(C_6H_4NO_2)_3$: Calcd. N, 8.9; Nb, 19.6%).

Results and Discussion

$Nb(C_6H_4NO_2)_4$ is a shining crystalline solid stable in a dry inert atmosphere. Moist air slowly converts it to the tris compound. The complex is freely soluble in all common organic solvents and is decomposed by water. The oxidation number of niobium, determined by oxidising known quantities of the tetrakis compound with standard iodine solution, is 4.00 ± 0.05 . It shows that during the formation of this complex in aqueous medium the Nb^{III} in the starting compound was oxidised to Nb^{IV} . To prove that the compound is not a mixed valence polymer³, its molecular weight was determined and the mean observed value was 590 *vis-a-vis* the required value of 581 for a monomeric unit. The molecular conductance value, $0.84 \Omega^{-1} cm^2$ in DMSO, proves it to be a non-electrolyte. These data more or less establish that the complex is really a tetrakis derivative which is further proved by its μ_{eff} value 1.53 B.M. at room temperature, being the same as that of tetrakis niobium(IV) complexes⁴⁻⁷.

$NbO(C_6H_4NO_2)_3$ is the product of controlled oxidation of the tetravalent complex, the control being really that of the water content. This is so susceptible to hydrolytic attack that the pentavalent complex can never be obtained in aqueous environment.

The electronic spectra of both the complexes in chloroform show 37.7 kK band for the ligand transition. The d-d band for $Nb^{IV}(C_6H_4NO_2)_4$ (d^1) is observed at 19.3 kK ($\xi = 3750$) obviously gaining intensity owing to charge transfer^{8,9}. The IR bands⁹⁻¹¹ are observed at 315 (Nb-N) and 450 cm^{-1} (Nb-O) for $Nb(C_6H_4NO_2)_4$. The Nb=O band in $NbO(C_6H_4NO_2)_3$ can be easily identified^{12,13} at 920 cm^{-1} which is obviously absent in tetrakis complex. The C=O band of the ligand is observed at 1665 cm^{-1} for the Nb^{IV} complex and at 1690 cm^{-1} for the Nb^{V} complex, while in $K[C_6H_4NO_2]$ the band is observed at 1610 cm^{-1} and in the free acid at 1700 cm^{-1} . The values are in conformity¹⁴ with the expectations.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. B. K. Sen of this Department and Swami Muktirupananda, Principal, R. K. M. Residential College, Narendrapur, for encouragement.

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Study of Lead(II) Chelates of Penicillins

PURUSHOTTAM B. CHAKRAWARTI, (MISS) C. P. TIWARI,
ANURADHA TIWARI and H. N. SHARMA

Chemical Laboratories, M. L. B. College, Bhopal-462 005

Manuscript received 20 May 1982, revised 21 January 1984,
accepted 17 June 1984

LEAD salts have been shown to induce renal adenomas and renal adenocarcinomas in rodents following administration by dietary and parenteral routes¹⁻³. In addition, carcinomas of the testis and adenomas of the adrenal, thyroid, pituitary, postate and lungs following chronic dietary administration of lead acetate to rats have been reported⁴. The carcinogenicity of tetraethyl lead has been tested following subcutaneous infection into neonatal Swiss mice⁵. Recent study in metal carcinogenesis in experimental animals has shown prohibition of tumours in the control rats receiving penicillin solutions⁶. Since cancer formation and its inhibition both are supposed to involve chelation⁷, the value of formation and thermodynamic constants of metal complexes of these drugs will give important information in the understanding of their biological activity.

Hence, in the present note we report the thermodynamic parameters and characterisation of the isolated complexes of Pb^{II} with penicillins, V and G (PV and PG).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of high purity, while the experimental details remain the same as in our previous communications⁸.

Stoichiometry of the various species formed was determined using conductometric titrations and the stability constants were computed by Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁹.

Thermodynamic parameters—the values of the changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) accompanying the metal ligand complex forming reactions have been calculated at various temperatures using the relations

$$\Delta G = -RT \log k$$

$$\Delta H = \frac{4.57 (d \log k)}{d (1/T)}$$

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T}$$

Equimolar solution of the metal and the ligand (penicillin G or V) in 1 : 2 ratio in 80% acetone-water (v/v) solution was refluxed for 4 h. The solution was then concentrated to one-fifth the original volume on a water bath. The complex was separated by vacuum filtration, washed with ether and dried under vacuum.

The composition of the complexes was ascertained by elemental analyses and the presence of the lattice water was estimated from the difference in the weight obtained on heating them to 110°. The results are recorded in Table 1. Ir spectra (KBr)

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF Pb^{II} CHELATESPG = C₁₆H₁₇O₄N₂SPV = C₁₆H₁₇O₄N₂S

Compd.	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)					
	C	H	N	S	M	H ₂ O
PG chelate	32.10 (31.70)	3.91 (3.74)	6.33 (6.41)	7.41 (7.33)	23.11 (22.89)	3.40 (3.52)
PV chelate	31.30 (30.62)	3.70 (3.60)	6.23 (6.19)	7.12 (7.07)	22.15 (22.89)	3.47 (3.40)

were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Model 237 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The conductometric titrations show formation of ML and ML₂ complexes between Pb^{II} and penicillin G and V, while pH titrations indicate removal of one proton during complexation of each molecule. The pH titrations did not indicate formation of 1 : 3 complex in these systems. All attempts to trace possibility of complexation of more than two molecules of the ligand gave negative results. This may be due to the steric hindrance caused by the bulky molecules of PG and PV. Thus, the complex formation may be as follows :

where HL = penicillin G or V.